

Suffering Unmasks God and Humans

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As Corona virus outbreak seems to be engulfing the entire human race one may wonder whether God has lost control of the universe? Or is He not caring for His creation which He created with much love, in His own image and likeness? Humanity is going through days of darkness, pain and affliction as Pope Francis says in his *Urbi et Orbi* prayer, “We find ourselves afraid and lost...caught off-guard by unexpected, turbulent storm...all of us fragile and disoriented...”. Hence hoping in the boundless mercy of God, he entrusts humanity to God.

At this point, a penetrating look into the reality of our own self both as individual and as human family and into God will help us to renew our love and communion with God, redefine our identity and to practice a reverential approach (a stewardship) to others and creation.

Book of Job and A Humanity Plagued by Covid-19

The point of the discussion here is not comparison between suffering of Job and our humanity plagued by Covid-19. All that we look for is some insight to our present position faced with this pandemic.

Book of Job is a beautiful piece of biblical literature that skilfully unmask what is true of God and of human beings faced with a question that is, human beings love and serve God because it pays to do so and God on his part rewards the virtue and punishes vice

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relinquishing his absolute sovereignty (cf. Job 1:9). The author of the Book of Job with extreme care and caution sheds profound insight into the truth of divine and human nature. The highly didactical book of Job tells us on the one hand how just God is in his great wisdom as is revealed in the ordering of

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the universe and how extremely caring he is for the created beings, big and small. On the other hand, it poignantly tells us how human beings needs to relate to God specially when surrounded by afflictions on every side. From both the sides it is a disinterested love, a love just for the sake of the other.

Unmasking of God

Job and his friends knew God through traditional wisdom and from the teachings of the elders. Job’s friends with all the traditional wisdom advised of God and his ways in the creation asking Job to accept their teaching (Job 4–38). Nostalgic of his past experiences of personal intimacy with God, Job searches God’s real character amidst his suffering. While Job recalls the intimacy of a trusting relationship with God (10:12; 12:4), he accuses God being unjust in his dealing with him.

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Avowing his innocence Job insists God to come in person to reveal his intentions to him, to prove His justice. In the avowal of his innocence Job crosses the human boundary and blames God to be unjust, in other words, he is tempted to be superior to God. God understanding the danger of Job’s position, that his instance of innocence has become the hurdle between the personal relationship with God, and further it will turn to be pride, in his great care corrects Job. The caring God does not blame Job or does not seem to take offence but asks Job to

comprehend deeply the wisdom and care of God imprinted in the cosmos.

The questions of God remain enigma for Job that he acknowledges God's Majesty and says that "I have heard of Thee by the hearing of the ear", meaning through the traditional teachings of wisdom and from the elders; "But now my eye sees Thee" meaning, he has come to experience him personally. (Job 41:5). In wonder and astonishment Job acknowledges the wisdom of God that designed cosmos, goodness which he extends even to the most insignificant creation and justice that rule the created order. He also acknowledges that he has been wrong by speaking about things about which he has no understanding. (Job 42:2-4). If God is just and caring to all His creation, will He not just to Job too, will He not take care of him? Therefore, Job surrenders his destiny with God.

As humanity has its limitation to comprehend God in his true nature, it often tends fashion a God of its own choice or convenience. The sufferings and afflictions in our personal life or that affect human family as in the case of COVID-19 are helps shed our fixations and to unmask the true nature of God.

Unmasking of True Human Self

Even though Job is no equal for Him, God asks him to gird up loins like a man and to answer him (Job 38:3). In spite his wretched state and infuriated words God acknowledges Job's human dignity and raises him from his low state. Job acknowledges that he has been speaking from derivative experience rather than from primary relationship with God. Consequently, he realizes that he has no claim on his personal integrity. In humility he stands before God and accept his mortality saying, "I retract, and I repent in dust and

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ashes" (Job 42:6). Thus, sufferings help us to shed human pride and arrogance and brings true perception of the self. As humanity

has its limitation to comprehend God in his true nature, it often tends fashion a God of its own choice or convenience. The sufferings and afflictions in our personal life or that affect human family as in the case of COVID-19 are helps to unmask our identity.

Job's loves and trust in God is expressed in his faithful devotion to God (1:1,5). God himself had high regard for him and call him "my servant Job". God's confidence in Job is expressed in his words "there is no one like him on the earth, a blameless and upright man, fearing God and turning away from evil." (Job 1:8). However, in His response to Job God does not make any **Reference** to Job's innocence. The book of Job teaches that there can be nothing in between God and human person even his/her own pursuit for virtue. An over emphasis of even virtues can become a obstacle to the divine-human communion.

Conclusion

Suffering is a mystery. The pain, loss and grief caused by Covid-19 is beyond compare but God is not far from His children who suffer. His heart is grieved for their misery and He bears us in His love. He will surely respond. We need to remember that God's response to Job was not as expected by Job, his friends or the readers. Similarly, His response to us may not be the one that we expect. Probably He wants us to know something more of the Mystery of God beyond our traditional knowledge of Him. Such a knowledge can be learned only from

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a personal experience and it will emerge as a new spirituality characterised by divine-human communion, re-discovery of personal identity and a reverential approach to the others and creation (stewardship).

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